

Raw Data and Replicates

Stanley et al.

Figure 1

A

B

Figure 2

Figure 3

D

Figure 4

Figure 4

B

Figure 5

* AccA abundance normalized to RNAP abundance to normalize for loading error. Timepoint 0 min set at relative 1.0.

Figure 6

Figure 7

A

Figure S1

A

Figure S2

A

B

Figure S3

B

C

